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Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. CHRISTA HOPE G. CORROS

Instructor II

Capiz State University, Dayao Satellite College

chgcorros@capsu.edu.ph

“BECOMING”

“I came across a meme on Facebook that said, “Lord, I don’t want to be on your strongest soldier’s list for the third year in a row.” It made me laugh, but it also stirred something deeper within me. It felt all too relatable. When we’re in the midst of pain, facing one challenge after another, it’s natural to question everything: Where is this leading me? What phase of life am I in? Why do I have to endure so much? Why can’t I have a simple, happy life like others seem to have?”

Life, much like nature, unfolds in phases, and suffering is an undeniable part of that journey. Allow me to frame this in a narrative: consider the pearl—a fitting analogy for a person enduring pain.

A pearl is a fitting analogy for a man who is suffering. Just as a pearl form when an irritant, like a grain of sand or a parasite, enters an oyster or clam, the mollusk responds by secreting layers of nacre to cover the irritant. Over time, this process, though painful, transforms the irritant into a beautiful pearl.

Similarly, suffering in life acts as an irritant that, when endured with resilience, can lead to personal growth and transformation. Just as a mollusk that has not experienced irritation cannot produce a pearl; individuals who avoid or escape suffering may miss out on significant personal development.

Life’s inevitable suffering can, paradoxically, be a privilege, offering the opportunity to be shaped into our finest selves. Viktor Frankl aptly noted, “Suffering ceases to be suffering the moment it finds its meaning.” Thus, through enduring suffering, we find deeper meaning and emerge transformed, just as a pearl emerges from the mollusk.